

Milestone 6

Pilot with first service and descriptions available

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TETTRIs

Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research, and Innovations

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Abstract:

This document is a short description of milestone 6 in the TETTRIs project, a software product which is a first version (pilot) of the marketplace for taxonomic e-services. The document provides a description of the developed software, objectives during implementation, the design and development process followed and a short outlook describing further development of the milestone into the deliverable D3.1 product.

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1. Introduction

This milestone is a first version (pilot) of the marketplace for taxonomic e-services. The milestone consists of a marketplace portal front- and back-end; and a Google Form with Apps Script to submit suggestions for new e-services to the marketplace back-end. It contains a few service descriptions to showcase that the pilot is fully functional. The front-end has a modern responsive design, suitable for display on both desktops and mobile devices. The front-end is designed to provide access to e-services descriptions but also to include taxonomic expertise and reference collections later in the project. The back-end is based on Cordra¹, open source software designed for managing digital objects provided by CNRI², the provider of the Global Handle System, the infrastructure that is used for e.g. serving DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers). The back-end is configured to be used with a Local Handle Server in production, to provide Handles as persistent identifiers for the service descriptions. The Handle records will include machine readable metadata to make the service descriptions machine actionable in line with the concept of FAIR Digital Objects, created Handles will get as prefix 20.500.14547.

The current setup is hosted by Naturalis and can be accessed at: '<https://cetaf-marketplace.dissco.tech>', but the intention is to fully host the application at a server managed by CETAF. For this reason, all references to: 'cetaf-marketplace.dissco.tech' in this report will be deprecated in the near future. The new domain name will become: 'marketplace.cetaf.org'. A static webpage is already hosted there and technical documentation for deployment by CETAF has been prepared³.

2. Objectives

Work package 3 in TETTRIs defines a set of objectives that relate to the development of a marketplace for taxonomic e-services and expertise. Task 3.1 is assigned to the e-services part. Based on the task description the following criteria were followed for implementation:

- Create a marketplace that is useful and easy to find for taxonomists and researchers.
- Provide a CETAF curated catalog that provides accurate information and can be sustained and updated in the future by piloting automated indexing of compliant service and resource descriptions to be served as FAIR Digital Objects.
- Focus on services and tools that are trustworthy and provide indicators for trustworthiness.
- The marketplace back-end is capable of providing FAIR Digital Objects.
- Create a structured and navigable index that is usable by different audiences.
- Connect demand and supply of taxonomic e-services in taxonomy.
- Work towards interoperability with existing service catalogs such as the EOSC Portal.
- Provide user support through the DISSCo helpdesk to serve a platform for users to get in contact with the e-service providers.
- Promote open science through focus on open source licensed software.

¹ <https://www.cordra.org/>

² <https://www.cnri.reston.va.us/>

³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wjX_dIJR70RarBR0UC0c4G_b-UecigKzHH8AWFC1-1

3. Design process

During the TETTRIs All-Hands meeting in Brussels, the work package members got together to discuss the fundamentals of the marketplace. A prerequisite was to collect potential user stories based upon the objectives that could be discussed on relevance and importance. Based on the results, a list of core user stories was created and considered the core of the marketplace's functionality. Ending the meeting, there was a consensus on what the marketplace should be and offer, however, ownership and the best fit technical architecture remained an open question.

With the provided user stories, the team started on creating early mock-ups (visual representations of the marketplace) in the [Design Document](#) and started discussing these in the regularly scheduled task 3.3 meetings with project partners. Each meeting, the mock-ups were a bit more refined, moving from stale lines and shapes, up until a fully interactive [Prototype](#) with a navigable index. This prototype sparked the discussion about the still debatable technical architecture and ownership of the marketplace as an application. Ultimately, CETAF intends to host and maintain the application. This decision directly affected the technical architecture in a sense that it should be maintainable by CETAF which has limited capacity in technical staff.

The final [Technical Architecture](#) adheres to all of the critical design specifications, which include the management rules set by CETAF, as well as the original user stories and feedback received from the work package team. It describes two separate applications: a front- and back-end, running in the same online environment. The [Front-end Application](#) allows users to interact with the marketplace via a graphical user interface (GUI). It is custom built using the React JavaScript library and acts as a one page application which asynchronously interacts with the application programming interface (API) of the back-end. The [Back-end](#) is constructed using the Cordra software, a kind of object store with a GUI on top. It both offers a good API as well as an internal handle server for creating persistent identifiers that are globally unique and resolvable.

Handle generation is an important requirement of the task as it hooks into the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) part of the application. Local handles in the Cordra software will be unique, but using the registration services of CNRI, a prefix can be ordered and published so all identifiers will be globally unique. Aside from that, CNRI provides a service called Handle.net that resolves global handles to local applications, making all e-service findable and easily accessible. The marketplace handle server has been registered at CNRI and received the prefix of: 20.500.14547. New e-services will receive an identifier starting with the prefix and ending with twenty random numbers or letters.

The GUI of Cordra allows users to add, edit or delete taxonomic e-services and tools. Together with CETAF, it was decided to leave these actions to its staff and call them admins. Normal users will be able to suggest new e-services through an external [Form](#), created within Google Forms. This form will be maintained by CETAF and be accessible via the marketplace. Suggested services are posted via a Google Apps Script to the marketplace back-end which, based on the provided information, creates draft records. Following this, CETAF staff will review the created records, act as executive editor and decide whether the suggested resources are suitable to publish to the marketplace catalog. Published records are visible for all users. If records are rejected, they will remain in the system but will not become public. Records can be deleted in the case of spam, but we aim to prevent spam from entering the system at all by implementing anti-spam measurements in the google form.

A taxonomic e-service record is built using a specially designed [Data Model](#). The model

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uses terms of schema.org and is constructed using JSON-LD. The structure is partly impacted by the now discontinued EOSC resource profile and should in principle contain all basic terms that define a taxonomic e-service in the context of the marketplace. The model contains one term from the Open Digital Specimen (ODS) definition called: topic discipline to aid users in searching for relevant services. It describes which topic discipline the taxonomic e-service relates to, for example: botany or zoology. The data model has extensively been reviewed by members of the task team.

Concluding, the design process resulted in a variety of individual products which together form the marketplace as an e-service.

4. Summary of products

The following products are delivered with this milestone report:

- Front-end application as the graphical user interface for the marketplace.
<https://cetaf-marketplace.dissco.tech>
- Back-end application providing an object store for saving taxonomic e-services, application programming interface and local handle server.
<https://cetaf-marketplace.dissco.tech/cordra>
- Google Form with Apps Script application for handling new taxonomic e-service suggestions.
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf6ug3jMZnZaZrP0WYv7GgFvnn06Qldi2GFekEqynwsoTCfUQ/viewform?usp=sf_link

5. Further development towards the deliverable

In further development towards deliverable D3.1 A pilot implementation for a taxonomic e-services and resources marketplace, which is due in November 2024, there will be a set of improvements which should be considered for implementation. These improvements are based on current experiences with the marketplace application, as well as new discussions within the work package team.

- Host the marketplace application as a service at the server of CETAF.
- Complete the Handle.net registration by extracting the necessary site information when deployed on the server of CETAF.
- Add additional terms to the data model that extend the information known about the taxonomic e-service submitter.
- Integrate the form for suggesting new taxonomic e-services in the front-end application instead of using Google Forms (requires Recaptcha and spam handling).
- Research authentication possibilities within Cordra, with the aim to authenticate CETAF staff in the front-end and develop a reviewing process, making direct access to Cordra by CETAF staff obsolete.
- Support markdown in the taxonomic e-service description so users can differentiate titles, paragraphs or special text.
- Add a quality indicator based on available metadata that helps CETAF staff to review and score taxonomic e-services as well as to provide added value to users of the marketplace.